

The Effectiveness of Utilizing Audio-Visual Learning Tools among TESL Undergraduates Higher Education institution in Malaysia

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Abstract: Audio-Visual tools are devices used in classrooms to encourage learning and make it easier and more interesting. This research analysed the Audio-Visual learning tools effectiveness among TESL Undergraduate students from a Private University in Ipoh. Moreover, another purpose of this study was to help students discover the most effective way of learning using Audio-Visual tools in the classroom. This study focused on the quantitative method and questionnaires were the main tool for this study. The questionnaire was administered to 30 students of TESL Undergraduates, and the collected data was analysed through the SPSS software. As a whole, this research found that incorporating Audio-Visual tools was effective as it enhanced students' English Language learning experience.

Keyword: Audio-Visual tools, Effectiveness, Auditory, Kinesthetic, TESL

INTRODUCTION

This study discusses that Audio-Visual learning tools are equipment and devices that will make any learning process effective and memorable. Audio-Visual learning tools are a type of material that help students in their learning process as they will use all these devices in their classroom and also comfort their learning activities by making them understandable and more interesting according to Shah (2015) as cited in Tareen, & Nazmine (2021). Many countries in this world have advanced technology, and many researchers also have proven that with media technology students will be able to study and score well in their education. This is because, with technology usage, students can use Audio-Visual tools in their classroom and help them in their learning process. Moreover, there are also some barriers we can adopt from the multimedia in a classroom such as any relationship between students and teachers. In this, we can say that there is a gap between the students and also the teachers according to Kurt & Ciftci (2012) as cited in Tareen, & Nazmine (2021).

It was suggested by Bajrami & Ismaili (2016) that audio visual materials can also aid English language learners' auditory comprehension. The structure of language consists of non-grammatical features that differ from the written language, which can enhance learners' comprehension and engage them. The connection between the classroom and the actual world helps students comprehend the connection between learning and practice. Thus, Bajrami & Ismaili (2016) is agreeable that AV materials are widely regarded as more effective and comprehensible than other media for students of second and foreign languages.

Furthermore, students should learn that referring to the help from pictures will help them understand even better. In addition, pictures, animations, and any kind of information presented on screen have a different learning process from printed text. Gilakjani (2012) as cited in Ho & Intai (2017) has stated that using effective learning materials such as Audio-Visual learning tools in learning will help students in scoring in their education at any level such as University. Moreover, using Audio-Visual learning tools as material in learning will enhance the students' deep understanding. Using technology in the learning process would change the setting of the classroom. This is because many types of gadgets can make a learning process more effective, such as projectors, smartphones, laptops, smartboards, etc. Besides, Audio-Visuals learning tools will enable students to sustain their motivation and interest in their learning process.

A good learning median can certainly support any kind of learning process. Audio-Visual learning tools have many advantages as the printed, hearing or images can become an attraction that is so strong for students in their learning process because these types of tools will help students to easier their learning. Moreover, Audio-Visual tools are very important in an education system. These devices used in a classroom will encourage learning and make it more interesting. In other words, Audio-Visual tools are the best tools for making teaching and learning more effective. Audio-Visual tools will also provide significant benefits in recalling, thinking, interesting imagination, and growth of a person.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning is a complex process where it involves many things. According to Shabiralyani, Hasan, Hamad, & Iqbal (2015), learning can happen in any way because it will refresh the skills, principles, facts, and new information in a time. Any kind of Visual tools or instructions that are used in a classroom will encourage the learning process. Shah & Khan (2016) highlighted that animation and information presented on the screen provided a different learning experience from printed text, which benefited the development of critical thinking. Audio-Visual tools are playing an effective and significant role in the learning process of both teachers and students. Apart from that, it also represents that, with the help of these devices' students gain detailed and in-depth knowledge.

Audio-Visual tools encourage a person's thinking and understanding skills according to Ho & Intai (2017). These devices have significant effects on the process of learning new things. The use of such tools makes a strong correlation with better understanding. It has been pointed out that audio-visual tools are beneficial in the learning process due to the audio-visual processing channels of the human mind which register pictures, words, and sounds in the sensory memory. Visual tools stir the enthusiasm of students and help the instructors to clarify ideas effectively. Audio-Visual resources can play a major role in making learning permanent. In this, we can say that Audio-Visual methods do seem to facilitate the acquisition, retention, and recall of lessons learned because they seem to evoke the maximum response of the whole organism to the situations in which learning is done according to Ho et al (2017).

Visual Auditory Kinesthetic Learning Theory

Figure 2.1: Visual Auditory Kinesthetics theory (Injadat 2018)

This theory has been adapted from Injadar (2018) to adapt this research. Moubayed (2018) et al. has stated that different people have different learning styles and they also have their strategies in their learning process. Moreover, some people learn verbally and some like doing things alone. In this, there are some theories or models that can be adapted to classify the learning process of learners. There are three most important models based on figure 1 that will be discussed in depth. Based on the Visual Auditory Kinesthetics (VAK) model, it is the simplest learning style model that can be used in any learning process. (VAK) stands for Visual Auditory Kinesthetics which involves the three main sensory receivers. Moubayed (2018) et al. has stated that this model assumes that a person either prefers to learn by seeing, hearing or doing tasks related to the subject.

Furthermore, Visual Learners are types of learners that prefer stimulants. For example, some students like to read and write something repeatedly for them to learn that particular thing. Moreover, Moubayed (2018) et al. has stated that some students also prefer diagrams, to learn something they can understand easily. Hence, students with this learning style prefer to use visual aids during lessons. For example, students can use visual aids charts, graphics, and colorful notes in their learning.

Moreover, Auditory learners are types of learners that prefer Auditory stimulation. This is because these types of learners like to discuss things and they prefer to talk about things and any discussion with their teachers. Moubayeh (2018) et al. has stated that they will analyse the tone, pitch and speed of speech to help them in understanding the content easily. Hence, these types of learners prefer to work in groups and discuss their ideas with others. Apart from that, they also prefer to have a summary at the end of the lesson.

Last but not least Kinesthetics learners prefer to learn when they move and do the tasks with their own hands. Moubayed (2018) et al. has stated that these types of learners prefer to move and tend to ask for more breaks and they will refocus on what they are doing. Moreover, Kinesthetics learners also have great hand-eye coordination and reactions.

METHODS

The researcher aims to use the survey design method to conduct the findings of this research through a quantitative approach. Moreover, on collecting the data and also analysis of the samples, questionnaires will be designed for this approach. Therefore, questionnaires were adapted for the students to answer the research question. Besides, Eyisi (2016) has stated that the quantitative data approach is a method that can save the researcher time and the researcher will get statistical data from this particular approach.

The main target samples or audience for this research are from the Faculty of Social Sciences BA TESL students from years 1, 2, and 3 and these samples are from one of the private universities that are located in Ipoh, Perak, Malaysia. The Bachelor of Arts in English Language Studies focuses on the theoretical aspects of the English language as well as its practical applications. It prepares students for effective English communication in a variety of contexts and circumstances. The main reason why the researcher is going to choose these particular samples is that these students will go through this main topic that will help them in the future and it will also help the researcher to achieve their main aim for this particular study.

Moreover, the target population consisted of first, second and third-year students. Hence, 30 students will be used for this study and it will consist of 9 male and 21 female students. This is because the sample for this research is limited to thirty samples and it will help the researcher to achieve a certain degree of accuracy in this particular study.

The sampling method that the researcher is using is non-probability sampling which will consist of convenience sampling. Moreover, non-probability sampling involves the selection of random selection that is based on particular data and it will allow the researcher to collect the data easily Showkat & Parveen (2017). However, under non-probability sampling, there is convenience sampling and, in this sample, the researcher will find the nearest person to collect the data and it is convenient for the researcher and respondent. This method can be used for quantitative types of data. The reason to use this method is to distribute the questionnaires to all the TESL students that are from the faculty of social sciences who are in their years one, two, and three as these study criteria fit the research requirement.

FINDINGS

The quantitative findings of this research that have been gathered from the responses were analyzed by using the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) application. A frequency analysis was applied and all the data were correctly coded and entered. Hence, descriptive statistics which consist of mean, standard deviations, percentages and frequencies were used.

The instruments that the researcher uses are questionnaires for this particular research. Based on this research, the main findings of this research will be conducted by using questionnaires. Krosnick (2018) has stated that a questionnaire is a set or way to gather data from the main subject of a study. Besides, only one set of questionnaires will be set to collect all the data from the responses. Therefore, for the quantitative data which are the questionnaires, the researcher has adopted different types of questions which are from Kaswa (2015) & Haider (2016). Moreover, the questionnaires that are adapted are from a valid and reliable source.

Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics for Views of Audio-Visual Learning tools

Items	Mean	Standard Deviation
1. I believe that teachers should always prepare Audio-Visual tools for their learning process.	3.43	0.728
2. I think that frequently used Audio-Visual tools can enhance my learning speed.	3.50	0.682
3. I have enough understanding of Audio-Visual tools.	3.40	0.724
4. I consider that Audio-Visual tools will encourage my involvement.	3.33	0.758
5. I believe that the classroom should be covered with different kinds of Audio-Visual tools.	3.47	0.776

Table 4.1 Demonstrates the analysis of Questions 1 to Question 5 of the questionnaire where the main of these questions focus on the views of students about Audio-Visual learning tools. Moreover, from table 4.5 we can observe that Question 4 has the lowest mean of 3.33 (SD=0.758) whereby Question 2 has the highest mean of 3.50 (SD=0.682). This explains that Audio-Visual tools may be beneficial in their learning process as they will help students to understand the lesson easily.

Table 4.2 Descriptive Statistics for Views of Audio-Visual learning tools

6. I believe when my lecturer involves Audio-Visual tools in the learning process, I can finish all the tasks easily.	3.43	0.728
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7. I observed that the non-use of Audio-Visual learning tools will provide low-quality academic performance.	2.80	0.997
8. I believe using Audio-Visual learning tools frequently can improve my academic performance.	3.33	0.844
9. I think that the use of Audio-Visual tools will bring a change to the classroom environment.	3.47	0.776
10. I consider the use of Audio-Visual tools should be used for a basic discussion of any topic.	3.17	0.913

Besides, in this section of the analysis, Questions 6 to Question 10 analyzed the view of students about learning from Audio-Visual learning tools. Hence, Question 7 has the lowest mean of 2.80 ($SD=0.997$) among the other 4 more questions and Question 6 has the highest mean of 3.43 ($SD=0.728$). As a result of this, it is possible to draw the inference that students have a variety of perspectives regarding the use of audio-visual learning tools to their individual learning processes.

Besides, the use of Audio-Visual tools in the English language provides an understanding of difficult concepts and this study shows that Audio-Visual tools are effective in increasing the understanding of students. Apart from that, in this study, it is found that students of TESL undergraduates have a moderate level of understanding of the effectiveness of utilizing Audio-Visual tools in their learning process.

Moreover, the VAK theory or model that is the Visual Auditory Kinesthetics model is suitable for language learning. This is because this model offers students the flexibility to utilize their learning styles which are the Visual Auditory and Kinesthetics styles. Hence, applying the VAK model in learning will also improve the intelligence of the student and one of the internal factors that will affect students' learning process. Therefore, by conducting and completing this study, the researcher was able to see the effectiveness of Audio-Visual learning tools among TESL undergraduate students and the importance of those tools for students in their learning process. Besides, the findings of this study have also contributed to identifying the effectiveness of interest of TESL undergraduate students in utilizing Audio-Visual learning tools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this research, there are a few recommendations that would be useful and should be taken into consideration. The analysis of the questionnaires indicated that the effectiveness of Audio-Visual learning tools among TESL undergraduate students was summed up with few gaps. Singh et al (2021) have recommended that appropriate teaching tools will establish the learning process for English language learners and improve their efficient skills.

Moreover, Suaib (2017) has recommended that teachers are suggested to utilize the Visual Auditory Kinesthetics learning style in the classroom as it can brighten the atmosphere of the classroom. Hence, the learning and teaching process will be presented in an enjoyable and relaxing atmosphere and it will give the students a sense of joy in the learning process.

Apart from that, teachers play an important role and need to create innovations in learning for both the use of models, methods and media that are appropriate to the characteristics of students so that the learning objectives can be achieved to the maximum as recommended by Kusumawarti et al (2020).

Therefore, Sit et al. (2021) has recommended that when teachers are teaching they should always incorporate

Audio-Visual tools in their teaching activities because students will understand more with the usage of visual tools. Besides, teachers are also suggested to update themselves about the proper use and integration of audio-Visual presentation by real objects or any tactile things during classroom teaching.

As for future research, the researcher can venture their studies into a wider scope of study whereby they attain more information from a larger number of students. Hence, teachers should consider that learning acquisitions vary and it will allow the Visual Auditory Kinesthetics learners to explore the content of the lessons from different methods and tasks offered by Malacapay (2019).

Therefore, the future researcher can use the qualitative method whereby the researcher can include interviews to collect better data and the researcher can ask the respondent's opinions and other suggestions about Audio-Visual tools.

The purpose of this study was to identify the effectiveness of Audio-Visual learning tools among TESL undergraduate students. Moreover, the findings and results of this study were all presented in a positive and recommended way. The data analysis revealed that the effectiveness of utilizing Audio-Visual learning tools among TESL undergraduate students is at a moderate level.

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